

THE PLACE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF THE POMEGRANATE FRUIT TODAY

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Abstract. *Pomegranate in Uzbekistan very ancient of times since cultivated will come. Pomegranate full red color the eye dazzles. Pomegranate not only delicious, maybe rich in vitamins, long years during also used in medicine is coming. From this except Pomegranate from the juice available paint great to himself special the taste and aroma , transparent brown color with separate stands Pomegranate from the fruits a person calming , nervous of tension will receive the tea preparation can Of this for ripe of fruit bark and curtains drying it is necessary.*

Keywords: *pomegranate generation (Punica L), fruit peel, pomegranate selection, agrotechnics, red color, C, P, B₆ and B₁₂ vitamins, pressing, fatty acids.*

Introduction

The pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) is a fruit-bearing deciduous shrub in the family Lythraceae, subfamily Punicoideae, that grows between 5 and 10 m (16 and 33 ft) tall.

The pomegranate was originally described throughout the Mediterranean region. It was introduced into Spanish America in the late 16th century and into California by Spanish settlers in 1769. They are widely cultivated throughout the Middle East and Caucasus region, north and tropical Africa, the Indian subcontinent, Central Asia, the drier parts of Southeast Asia, and the Mediterranean Basin. The fruit is typically in season in the Southern Hemisphere from March to May, and in the Northern Hemisphere from September to February.

As intact sarcotestas or as juice, pomegranates are used in baking, cooking, juice blends, meal garnishes, smoothies, and alcoholic beverages, such as cocktails and wine.

Uzbekistan Republic Ministers " Fergana" court in the region pomegranate to grow increase and the field development on measures " dated October 4, 2018 No. 791 Ferghana in the region pomegranate grower farms organize to achieve [1]

Pomegranate in Uzbekistan very ancient of times since cultivated will come. His homeland Azerbaijan, Iran, and Afghanistan. Pomegranate There are 2 species of the genus Punika L. Theirs one, i.e. of pomegranate cultural and wild (*P. granatum*) forms Medium Asia, Transcaucasia and in Dagestan grows. Other (*P. potopunica*) - wild of type the fruit eat it won't be. [2]

Pomegranate Medium Asia in the republics of the Caucasus back in countries mainly Azerbaijan Krasnodar in his country, Crimea in the region, South in Kazakhstan and in Dagestan planting is grown. Plantable cultural pomegranate selection the most good different types choose and high agricultural technology application the way with wild from pomegranate released.

Pomegranate from the fruits a person calming , nervous of tension will receive the tea preparation can Of this for ripe of fruit bark and curtains drying it is necessary From him after while tea or another to drink crushed dry from pomegranate a little to add can . [2]

Pomegranate the fruit all of fruits the king is considered His full red color the eye dazzles. Pomegranate not only delicious , maybe rich in vitamins , long years during also used in medicine bride from fruits is one Pomegranate its usefulness is recognized being , then of the organism good activity to show for all necessary vitamins there is If you meat Productive food consumption if you don't and if you are a vegetarian, of course that's it fruit your table on constant respectively to be need Because in it meat in the product There are 15 amino acids available. In it again main which is C, P, B₆ and B₁₂ vitamins there is Pomegranate again iodine , potassium , calcium , iron and silicon such as rich in minerals. [3]

Pomegranate from the juice available paint great to himself special the taste and aroma, transparent brown color with separate stands in the water and in alcohol good it dissolves and 68-72% dry substances own into takes _ Paint of syrup biological Product Name, Katelan and another things there is.

Pomegranate juice pressing through is taken. Pomegranate squeeze from the exit after 46-48% of pomegranate remains, which is called " Pomegranate ". new kind of brandy work release _ Transparent brown the color is great the taste and aroma, power 450. contagious diseases, dysentery, periodontal disease and others [4]

Pomegranate top from the part dry inside while good ripe and watery to be need Because you pomegranate skin smoother on time hang up received if you are in that case pomegranate yet good have matured unripe will be That's why for pomegranate skin more dry to be need Pomegranate skin to us his ripe or immaturity about to know enable creates.

Pomegranate juice very useful being, him blood scarcity disease, atherosclerosis, bronchial in asthma, angina, diabetes in diseases consumption to do recommendation will be done. From this in addition to this of fruit particles organism for important lipids source is because they are in the composition dry 12 to 20% by weight fatty acids there is Various different fatty acids big with separate stands unsaturated acids: linoleic and linolenic, Punic, olein and palmitin fatty acids there is. [4]

Pomegranate of seeds chemical composition :

- water (85%);
- sugar (10%) mainly fructose and glucose;
- organic acids (1.5%), they to the composition ascorbin , citrus and owner acids enters;
- such as polyphenols, flavonoids (anthocyanin). bioactive structural parts.

His chemical composition in terms of pomegranate is a whole vitamin-mineral complex. Normal functioning of the body for necessary has been all substances there is Fruit 15 seeds are

important amino acid, C, P, B₆ and B₁₂ vitamins, skin collection and binder substances, colored pigments, organic acids own into takes. From this besides, pomegranate fruits iodine, potassium and rich in calcium, iron, silicon. This from the composition come came out without, fruit main hematopoietic to products belongs to. [3]

100 g of pomegranate own into takes :

- 0.7 g of proteins;
- 14.5 g of carbohydrates;
- 0.6 g of fat.

Pomegranate the fruit calories amount up to 100 g an average of 72 kcal that to know need. Fruit the environment in temperature one how many day during nutritional value save remains. His contained tannins due to, it to the joints against and to inflammation against properties have, this intestine colic or gaseous gas during intestine mucus to the floor useful effect shows. Citrus acid because of pomegranate urine ac

Recently conducted studies fruit in the composition green tea and red to wine than three even a lot of antioxidants that there is showed. This antioxidants blood in the veins cholesterol of plates appear of being prevention get, in arteries the pressure in order put and of cells early aging and their oxidation prevention get through healthy blood rotation system in storage important role plays.

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